

An astronomy centered approach to relativity

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Abstract

This article presents the story and derivation of relativity through a fictional story as well as through history, developing a new view of relativity, though mathematically equivalent to the standard formalism, conceptually distinct, computationally easier and perfect for astronomy.

We look at some applications of the mathematics we develop; some are standard and others promise new calculational methods in astrophysics.

A man wakes up in a room. It is a cubical room. He is the only one there. There is nothing outside the room.

The man, let us call him hombre, starts exploring the room. In the middle of the room, a ball bounces up and down without an end, from one side to another. The man floats freely, and after a while he cannot tell the walls from each other so he marks 4 corners of the room and calls them O, X, Y and Z.

With nothing to do, he comes up with the ideas of lines, points, planes, directions, distances and relations such as parallel and perpendicular; all derived from what he sees in the room.

He then remarks that the ball makes jumps between the points $(L/2, L/2, 0)$ to $(L/2, L/2, L)$ with each number corresponding to a distance along 3 perpendicular axes, X, Y & Z and L representing the length of the room. Bored, he begins counting the number of times the ball has bounced.

Then suddenly he realises that next to his room in the positive X direction, there sits another room. It looks identical, with a person inside, also counting the bounces of the ball.

These two men, let's now call them hombre A and hombre B are astonished to discover the other room. They both want to believe that the other room is the *other* room, and that theirs is the primary. After spending some time scrutinising, they realise that both rooms are identical, and even the balls bounce in sync.

At this point hombre A has a brilliant idea, perhaps a crazy idea. He wants to assign a location to the point in hombre B's room where the ball bounced. So far he had been assigning coordinates based on the distances from 3 specific walls, and now he wanted to assign coordinates to a point outside the walls, in another room.

Hombre A, to mitigate this problem, declares that he could extend his walls further in his imagination and measure distances from where the wall *would* be.

He finds out that since the hombre B's room is following his room in the X direction, the distances measured by hombre B in Y & Z, should be identical while the distances in X should all be larger by "L" .

For any point x_B, y_B, z_B then:

$$x_B = x_A - L \quad (1)$$

$$y_B = y_A \quad (2)$$

$$z_B = z_A \quad (3)$$

What the hombres have come up with is the most basic formulation of relativity. So basic in fact, that we only call it translational symmetry. The laws of physics do not change, i.e. are invariable, in all places. No room is supreme.

At this point we should also append that the orientation of these rooms or how much time has passed also do not change the laws of physics.

The assumptions may seem too basic yet when discussing relativity or coordinate transforms one needs to be very careful in these exact places.

After many bounces of their central balls, the hombres become good friends.

This is when they notice two more rooms far in the horizon. These rooms, arranged back to back just like theirs, seemed to grow in size, hence they must be approaching the hombres A & B. This is a cause for excitement and great debates. These are moving rooms. How could they be moving? What is propelling them? What happens if they let a ball be free?

In the rooms of hombre A & B, if they kept a ball at a particular X, Y & Z location, it would remain at those coordinates indefinitely. They would ascribe those coordinates to the ball, sure, but those coordinates would not change.

Since they had already extended their coordinate systems beyond their rooms, they believed that they could do that indefinitely. In particular, they believed that the hombres in rooms that were moving, if they let a ball go, it would also remain at the x,

y & z coordinates that A & B assign.

Hombre A then remarked that if they drop a ball and it remains stationary for us; then those inside the room would see it travel backwards and then eventually hit the wall. To this, hombre B answered that they would consider it normal. Afterall, they are the moving rooms.

Let us talk about the same debate as above in our real world. If you were blind or never looked up at the sky, you would be convinced that everything you touch or stand on, is fixed in space. Even if you looked up at the sky, the Sun, the Moon and the stars would appear to rise and set, rotating above our fixed ground.

A few visionary astronomers such as Aryabhata (476-550 CE) asserted that it is the spherical Earth which rotates while the stars remain fixed in space. However correct this idea was, it was still rejected by future commentators, for “If the Earth moved, the birds who fly out for food could never return to their nests as the Earth would have moved away”.

This was the belief in the universality of space. In this belief, objects were either stationary or in a state of motion.

When the moving rooms became closer, hombres A & B were shocked to discover that these rooms were also identical in construction to theirs, including the central ball which bounced back and forth from the same points in their rooms, and obviously at different points in the extended coordinate systems of hombres A & B.

At this point hombres A & B got acquainted with the incoming hombres, who were called hombres α & β .

A & B asked α & β to drop a ball, expecting it to remain in one place in their system; however to their great surprise the ball remained in place with respect to the rooms α & β and moved uniformly in the systems of A & B.

While A & B were trying to digest this fact, α & β brought up an objection which added to their confusion even more. α & β asked why A & B were calling them “moving” while it is A & B who are moving.

It turned out that α & β had lived the same life as A & B at this point, waking up in stationary rooms and then seeing two rooms slowly travel towards them.

A & B could not accept that they had been travelling all this while, but at the same time, they could not devise any experiment that could prove that the rooms α & β were moving.

Hombre B remarked how with 1, B’s measurements could be converted to A’s and vice versa. Once A subtracted “L” from his X measurements, his measurements would match those of B. B wondered whether the same could be achieved for the rooms α & β . This time, they faced a challenge. The distance between the sets of rooms changed continuously.

Hence they needed a number, an idea of a number, that increased by its very definition. But at what rate would it increase, who would keep track? Very simply, they decided to count the number of times their central balls bounced back and forth, and they would keep a count henceforth. Since the ball bounced back and forth slowly, they could only count in integers and not in between them.

Indeed, they could imagine that the ball travelled endlessly instead of bouncing, farther and farther away, and the coordinate of the ball then became the ever increasing ‘time’-number that they needed.

When the “moving” rooms passed overhead of the rooms A & B, A noted that the edge of the room travelled equal distances between two bounces of the ball. He called this

distance as “v”. If they started counting time the moment the origin of room α had an x-coordinate of 0, the origin-corner of this room (α) would be at a distance $v \cdot t$ after time t .

Hence, A writes down:

$$x_{\alpha} = x_A - v \cdot t \quad (4)$$

$$y_{\alpha} = y_A \quad (5)$$

$$z_{\alpha} = z_A - L \quad (6)$$

For their particular arrangement, assuming that their measurements could extend indefinitely in the void.

At this point, B raised two questions:

- 1) If the balls slow down or speed up, is there any way we would know?
- 2) Can we use the same relationship to get from x_A to x_{α} ?

A admitted that beyond their perception, they would not know if the balls slowed down. As for the second question, the balls were assumed to bounce in sync, and we saw that all rooms were equivalent, so yes.

A keen reader would have observed that at this point we have reached Galilean Relativity. When the geocentric model in which the Earth neither rotated nor moved was beginning to be discarded, one needed to explain how we could be moving when we do not feel a force’ why if we drop a stone, it does not remain “in place” while we move away from it.

Relativity, as described by Aryabhata in the 5th century CE, began to take a more formal description. It was shown by an experiment conducted on a steadily moving boat that a stone falls vertically down only when seen from the boat, while it falls in a parabola as seen by a person standing on a river bank.

Rotation and movement of the Earth, though proposed by some ancient Greeks, were difficult pills to swallow.

Not too long after Galileo, a man observing and noting down the times of eclipses of Jupiter’s moon Io was about to stumble onto a great discovery; one which would shred the idea of a “present”.

As time went by, the hombres created a clock that used the central bouncing ball for calibration. They also realised that for moving objects, they needed to assign a time

coordinate to every set of position coordinates.

One day, hombre B discovered that he can move his room around in space. Now they had the opportunity to test the assumptions they had made before.

Particularly, they decided to check whether being in a different point in space affected the frequency of the central ball.

So, B moved his room some distance away. A was flabbergasted at what he was seeing. If he waved at B, B would take a while to wave back. While B's ball bounced at the same frequency, it was out of sync with A's ball; it was lagging behind.

When B came back, A expected that B had observed the same effect as him: that is, B should have observed that A's ball was leading and B's was lagging.

What B reported shocked them both. B observed that A's ball lagged behind B's ball. This led to a confusion. Whose ball was lagging and whose was leading? Both could not be true!

To test this effect again, B moved a distance away again, this time moving twice as much distance and he observed that A's ball lagged behind by twice as much longer. The effect reduced as he came closer and then the balls bounced in sync again.

This revealed to them something interesting about their world. Distance and Time were linked together. Upon coming back, B suggested that maybe both of them were equally right. If an observer were to be situated at the midpoint of these rooms, he would see the balls of A & B bounce in sync. To this, A remarked that true, but he would still not be seeing them in "real" time.

Nonetheless, they wrote down the empirical relationship they discovered as follows:

$$x_B = x_A - D \mid x_A = x_B + D \quad (7)$$

$$t_B = t_A - \frac{D}{c} \mid t_A = t_B + \frac{D}{c} \quad (8)$$

Where D is the distance between their rooms, c being the proportionality constant which determines the lag and (x_A, t_A) & (x_B, t_B) describing the coordinates of an event that they witness further along the shared X axis.

While B was away he noticed a tiny explosion further down his +ve X axis. When he returned to A; he saw that A had written down a bigger time coordinate than B. This made things clear to them. Different observers observed the same event at different distances and times. The choice of the origin also affected the time coordinates. Now if they wanted to convert the other's coordinates they had to use the new formula.

What A & B just discovered is what we refer to as the “finiteness of the speed of light”, or what we would refer to as “**photobremia**” in this paper. *Photo* standing for light and *bremia* standing for lag, being late.

This phenomenon is deeper than light, as in our current belief, c is the speed of causality itself. Even information takes time to travel.

This effect came to light when Ole Rømer was observing and cataloguing the eclipse times of Jupiter's closest satellite: Io. This was to serve as a universal clock for sailors at sea, who could observe an eclipse of Io to find out the time back on land, and then using the sunrise time they could calculate their timezone and hence the longitude. Clocks could not be taken aboard rocking ships back then.

A clock is expected keep making its periodic motions at a constant unchanging rates. Jupiter-Io system showed failed to meet this requirement.

If you noted the time of the eclipse when Jupiter-Io was the closest to the Earth, then months later you would find that the eclipses were occurring a few minutes later than when you would have expected them. This meant that light bouncing off of Jupiter took some time to reach us. At that time, the semi-major axis of the Earth's orbit around the Sun was not yet measured; hence Rømer could not calculate the speed of light but remarked/calculated that light must take about 20 minutes to cross the diameter of Earth's orbit.

This now meant that two lightening strikes may not be universally simultaneous. An observer closer to a strike would observe it first. The pervasive idea of time in classical physics was broken. When a school student calculates the path of a ball thrown under the influence of gravity, she assigns a position to each point in time; but underneath lies the implicit assumption of universal time.

Indeed for ordinary speeds and/or ordinary distances, the effects of *photobremia* are too insignificant. For astronomical purposes, the effects are too large to ignore.

A diligent student would have noticed at this point that this is not how the time of an event is recorded in standard relativity. Time in standard relativity is observer independent. In the story of A & B, they would subtract $\frac{x_A}{c}$ & $\frac{x_B}{c}$ from the times of observation and hence agree upon the time of the event. In standard relativity the break in simultaneity would come only when there is movement, not through separation.

There are a few reasons why we prefer our idea of time of an event:

1) In astronomy, converting from the time we observe an event to its “real” time of occurrence by subtracting the light-travel-time lag is impractical for most purposes as distances are known imprecisely or not at all. Time coordinates of events happening in other galaxies would be placed in the eras when dinosaurs roamed the Earth. The standard practice in astronomy is noting down the dates of events and observations when they were taken and not when they “really” occurred.

2) It is also easier to think about simultaneity when you see two events occur together, instead of imagining an observer at the spatial midpoint.

3) The intuition for the relativity of simultaneity and the later derivation of the special relativistic transform flows more easily and more intuitively, and the mathematics is simpler.

Even at this point we are in a position to do some real research. Imagine a rod rotating. A very long rod, a distance away from you. Since you would see older images of the rod’s endpoints, a rigid rod would appear as a spiral to you. When we image a far away galaxy, its spiral arms appear more spiral-ly from this photobremic effect. We shall soon produce a simulation of what the galaxy would look like when corrected for photobremia.

Now let us return to our story and see what the hombres are about to discover.

During B’s trips back and forth, A had begun figuring out how it is that as the room B receded, the clocks fell out of sync and how when the room came back they were back in sync.

There was only one way. B’s clock ticked slower as the room receded, falling behind, and then ticked with the same frequency but lagged behind when the room came to rest. When it approached back, B’s clock ticked faster, catching up and finally coming back to sync.

(x', t')
✱
 (x, t)

Hence A suggested the following to B:

$$x' = x - vt \mid x = x' + vt' \quad (9)$$

$$t' = t - \frac{vt}{c} = t\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \mid t = t' + \frac{vt'}{c} = t'\left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right) \quad (10)$$

Where (x,t) & (x',t') are describing an event which occurred ahead of B while B travelled in $+x$ direction.

Hence if for A, two events occurring at the same spatial location were separated by time ΔT , B would measured the same difference as $\Delta T(1 - v/c)$, a shorter duration as B's clock appears to tick slower.

If two events occur at the same spatial location at different times for B as he moves to $+x$, he would find that A would calculate that interval as $\Delta T'(1 + v/c)$.

Now not just simultaneity, but the rate of passage of time was also thrown into question.

There was no longer a standard rate of flow of time.

Additionally, A remarked that B moved slower while travelling away and faster when coming closer. B however claimed that he kept the same speed both ways.

Then they realised that B must be travelling at the same speed, however when he travels farther away, A finds out later and later. He must be “really” at a farther location than where he appears.

Hence assuming that he travelled at the same speed both ways, at 'v', he must appear to travel slower when going away and faster when approaching.

then:

$$v_{apparent} = \frac{(c \cdot v_{real})}{(c \pm v_{real})} \quad (11)$$

When going away, the sign in the denominator is positive, and when coming closer it is negative.

Please see the appendix for the derivation of 11.

Now we have arrived at the concept of time dilation. Indeed Rømer noted that the period of Io shrunk roughly by 16 seconds out of some 43 hours when we were headed right towards Jupiter and grew by the same amount when we were moving away directly. This is of course the only way the eclipse times would begin lagging. We shall refer to the equations 9 and 10 as **Rømerian transform**.

This time dilation and contraction effect is currently viewed by physicists as a “Doppler” effect. We wholeheartedly disagree with this view and recognise it as time dilation/contraction.

Also note that $t' = t(1 - v/c)$ and $t = t'(1 + v/c)$ do not agree with each other. However, for $v \ll c$, $1/(1 \pm v/c) \approx 1 \mp v/c$ and hence in the small speeds domain it is safe to use this relation.

A naive error was made during the derivation of the Rømerian transform, that the time lag between small distance moved by the room while light travelled from one room to another was not considered. We shall correct it soon. However, accounting for this error would still

keep the above problem intact.

Apparent velocities are important. Imagine that you are looking at the sky, at the star Betelgeuse. It looks fine for a moment and then it explodes. A minute later, charged particles expelled by the supernova explosion flare up the night sky atmosphere. Now, if you were asked to calculate the speed of these particles; knowing that the star lies ~ 500 ly away, you may divide 500 ly by 5 minutes to get the speed as 100 light years per minute, which is $365.2422 \times 24 \times 60$ times faster than the speed of light!

But is this truly ‘super-luminal’ motion? No, you calculated only the apparent velocity. Indeed you shall see, if you could observe, the particles appear to travel 500 light years in 5 minutes; but you are forgetting that light itself took 500 years to reach here, and hence they are slower than light. Now you can calculate the real velocity.

Q. As an exercise, calculate the speed of the ‘super-luminal’ ejecta if it appears to approach us at a speed of $10c$.

For the rest of our discussion, we won’t dive back into the story, rather stay here and develop the math further.

Another important note here is that positions-of objects would also appear at different locations based on their speeds. If you imagine an asteroid rushing towards your spaceship, since the image you see of it is outdated, it would ‘really’ be closer than where it appears. You may calculate the *real* position by converting the apparent speed to the “real” one and multiplying it with time.

However, there is no reason to panic. Even if the asteroid is “really” closer than where it appears, it would never hit you invisibly. The image of the asteroid and its “real” body shall hit you simultaneously.

In fact, we maintain that you are entirely justified in treating apparent objects, their positions, times and lengths as real; as there is no contradiction or discontinuity caused by it.

We formulate this postulate as follows:

“Every observer is entitled to consider their view as valid.”

Hence if you see Betelgeuse explode, you write down today’s date as the time of occurrence and not backdate it to 1500AD or something. For all intents and purposes, you may call the position of the object based on where you see it, without calculating the “real” position.

Also note that we already have length contraction and dilation. An object travelling away would appear shorter in the direction of motion as we would see the farther end at a slightly earlier time than the closer end. Conversely, an object approaching us would appear longer than an identical object at rest. We shall soon see the formulas for this later.

At present we have two errors to fix in the Rømerian transform and get it to speed with

special relativity.

The first error was that we did not take into account a small movement of the moving room while the light passed from one room to another.

Imagine a small explosion right of room B, the information first reaches B and then A. From A's point of view, if he observes the event at time t_A , B would not have been a distance $v \cdot t_A$ apart then, but slightly smaller than that, as he saw it first and moved forward. From B's point of view; he sees the event at t_B but A keeps moving away until A finally sees it; so the distance between them must be a little larger than $v \cdot t_B$. Recall that t_A & t_B are not expected to match; even if room B was stationary with respect to room A.

Hence forth we shall refer to (x_A, t_A) as (x, t) & (x_B, t_B) as (x', t') . We shall assume the other spatial dimensions to be unaffected, with motion being along the X axis and the event taking place to the right of B and the origins of the rooms coinciding with at $t=t'=0$.

We keep referring to them as *rooms* instead of *frames* as *frames* are now purely mathematical and imaginary, attached to no real object while the word *room* keeps you grounded.

The derivations of both corrections are attached in the appendix, and the reader is encouraged to derive these on her own.

With the correction now;

$$x' = x - \frac{c \cdot v}{c + v}t \quad | \quad x = x' + \frac{c \cdot v}{c - v}t' \quad (12)$$

$$t' = t - \frac{v}{c + v}t \quad | \quad t = t' + \frac{v}{c - v}t' \quad (13)$$

or

$$t' = \frac{c}{c + v}t \quad | \quad t = t' \frac{c}{c - v} \quad (14)$$

Let us first appreciate how nice it is that our relation between the time coordinates is not dependent on the spatial coordinates at all.

However, notice that both $t' = t(1/1+v/c)$ and $t = t'(1/1-v/c)$ cannot be simultaneously true. In the case of $v/c \ll 1$, it would be the case that $1/(1 \pm v/c) \approx (1 \mp v/c)$; however in the general case we have a problem. What did we do wrong?

We were headed to this contradiction when we decided to use the same 'c' for both of them.

For a singular event occurring at x and x' (same location but different coordinates for the two observers), Both A & B cannot imagine an expanding sphere of light at the same time. If A assumes that it's a sphere expanding at the simultaneous rate of c in all directions at a uniform rate, then he should conclude that B is rushing to meet the wavefront, finding a larger value for c . Conversely if B assumes that it is a sphere for him, he should believe

that A is running away from the wavefront and should find a smaller value for c .

We can solve this problem by either saying that A is truly stationary or B is truly stationary.

In the first case, we substitute ' c ' for ' $c+v$ ' for B's side:

$$x' = x - \frac{c \cdot v}{c+v}t \mid x = x' + \frac{(c+v)v}{c+v-v}t' = x' + \frac{(c+v)v}{c}t' \quad (15)$$

$$t' = t \frac{c}{c+v} \mid t = t' \frac{c+v}{c+v-v} = t' \frac{c+v}{c} \quad (16)$$

Now, as you could see t' & t agree with each other, however substituting x in terms of x' & t' in A's equation does not lead to equality.

We could work on solving that problem, but should we? In the above case, the room A carries a special importance. It is the frame in which the sphere of causality or light grows in all directions equally at c while others would need to use different values and would not see it as a sphere.

Is there any reason why A should be special or treated by convention to be special? For, in the absence of A as well; B should be able to measure his difference with the speed of light.

Experience has shown us that no such frame of reference could be found. Before Albert Einstein disrupted the scene, physicists were keen on finding the "ether-rest-frame", a frame of reference where light travels in all directions at the same speeds. Luminiferous ether was the medium in which light travelled as a wave, and clearly as air in which light travelled as a wave, and clearly as air has a rest frame in which you are flying with the wind and do not feel it; there had to be a frame in which the "ether rest frame" was not felt.

In his 1905 paper, a 26 year old Einstein boldly ridiculed ether and denied that it exists [1], restoring relativity albeit with bold implications. As it slowly turned out, ether was not disproven to exist, rather it was not possible to detect the ether wind. It could be there, but you cannot find it. Einstein shifted his stance and remained with relativity as it was in his opinion more soothing to the intellect than assuming the existence of ether wind you could not detect. By the 1920s he famously reversed his view on ether [3], restoring it in a new life and explaining why it was necessary for the theory of relativity, special and general.

In this paper, we shall stick with relativity, as we have; without making strong comments on whether it is a conventional choice or reality.

Now, we must make the equations agree with each other. If you transform (x,t) to (x',t') and (x',t') to (x,t) ; you should find the same (x,t) . In other words, the transforms must be inverses of each other. At the moment, they are not.

So let us assume that there is a linear relationship between (x,t) & (x',t') , and we are

missing some factors.

Hence, assume:

$$x' = \alpha_1 \left(x - \frac{c \cdot v}{c + v} t \right) | x = \alpha_2 \left(x' + \frac{c \cdot v}{c - v} t' \right) \quad (17)$$

$$t' = \beta_1 \frac{c}{c + v} t | t = \beta_2 \frac{c}{c - v} t' \quad (18)$$

We have assumed four different constants to be general.

Writing the transforms as matrices and then setting their matrix multiplication to identity matrix, then using the four resulting identities to reduce the number of unknowns, we get:

$$x' = \frac{c + v}{c} \frac{1}{\beta_2} \left(x - \frac{c \cdot v}{c + v} t \right) | x = \frac{c}{c + v} \beta_2 \left(x' + \frac{c \cdot v}{c - v} t' \right) \quad (19)$$

$$t' = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) \frac{1}{\beta_2} \frac{c}{c + v} t | t' = \beta_2 \frac{c}{c - v} t' \quad (20)$$

We have expressed α_1 , α_2 & β_1 in terms of β_2 .

We must impose some condition now, which would allow us to determine what β_2 is.

You might suggest imposing $x' = ct'$ then $x = ct$; or in other words something travelling at the speed of light should have the same speed in both the frames. However, this condition is satisfied for all values of β_2 , you may check it yourself, and this is due to us assuming it implicitly in our derivation.

Here we coin a new word, **photostegia**.

Photostegia is the principle which requires all observers to observe the same speed for causality/light in vacuum. *Stegia* comes from Greek for a “roof”.

All these infinite solutions for 19 and 20, each with a different value of β_2 , constant or variable (e.g.: $\beta_2 = 1, 500, v^2/c^2, (1 - v^5/c^5)...$), are **photostegic**; they admit the condition of constancy of speed of light.

However, they are all not *relativistic*.

For a transform pair to be relativistic, it must look symmetric. In fact, if $T(v)$ is the forward transform; then:

$$T(v) = T^{-1}(-v) \quad (21)$$

is the condition we impose for relativity.

With this condition, we finally arrive at:

$$x' = \sqrt{\frac{c + v}{c - v}} \left(x - \frac{c \cdot v}{c + v} t \right) | x = \sqrt{\frac{c - v}{c + v}} \left(x' + \frac{c \cdot v}{c - v} t' \right) \quad (22)$$

$$t' = \sqrt{\frac{c-v}{c+v}}t = \sqrt{\frac{c+v}{c-v}}t' \quad (23)$$

You may check the appendix for the full derivation, but I recommend you try to derive it on your own.

If you substitute t for $t - x/c$, hence shifting to the coordinates of standard relativity's formalism, you shall get the Lorentz transform back.

Do note that we are using apparent times yet "real" positions & velocities in this transform.

Now let us see some immediate use cases and applications of this transform. The first thing you'd note is that the times and space coordinates have been *scaled*.

Let us simplify the scale factor.

$$\sqrt{\frac{c+v}{c-v}} = \frac{c+v}{\sqrt{c^2-v^2}} = \frac{1+v/c}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \quad (24)$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{c-v}{c+v}} = \frac{c-v}{\sqrt{c^2-v^2}} = \frac{1-v/c}{\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}} \quad (25)$$

For $v/c \ll 1$:

$$\left(1 \pm \frac{v}{c}\right)\left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2} \approx \left(1 \pm \frac{v}{c}\right) \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + \dots\right) \quad \text{ignoring higher order terms.} \quad (26)$$

$$\approx \left(1 \pm v/c + \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + \dots\right) \quad (27)$$

You shall immediately notice that the v/c term comes from Rømer ("Doppler term") & the $v^2/2c^2$ term comes from Lorentz-Einstein. The first one from photobremia and the second one from photostegia. The photobremic term is dependent on the direction of motion, i.e. incoming rooms appear to have a faster clock and appear elongated and outgoing rooms have slower clocks and appear shortened. However the $v^2/2c^2$ is always positive, it always makes moving clocks tick slower and lengths shorter (wait until we see about lengths) regardless of the direction. Hence a clock that moves away and comes back would be found in sync as the second term does not average out to zero (however we should refrain from discussing the 'twin paradox' until we figure out the effect of acceleration on apparent physics).

This is of course in the case of $v/c \ll 1$, for illustrative purposes.

Note the transformation of the time coordinate is *independent* of the x-spatial coordinate and this is because how far away the event occurs is immaterial to the time coordinate, only the distance between the rooms decides the difference between times of observation of an

event, which is a linear function of time elapsed since the origins coincided.

This is in contrast with the Lorentz transform where time has explicit space dependence which makes computations more cumbersome.

Let us see an important application of the time dilation we just calculated.

We have a great potential to make important corrections is with periodic variable stars, particularly those which have a well measured period-luminosity(-metallicity) relation; which we use to calculate real distances to them through the measurement of their periods and their apparent magnitudes.

For example, consider a Cepheid variable with a radial velocity of 300 km/s; still much smaller than the speed of light which is roughly 300,000 km/s; the correction term then becomes $(1 \pm v/c)$ or $(1 \pm 0.1\%)$. A Cepheid variable with such speed in the inward direction would appear to pulsate faster than its real period and we must correct for it (similarly for outward radial velocity). 0.1%, however, is smaller than the errors present in measurement and the period-luminosity relation, of which there are multiple instances.

But, when we look at the cosmic distance ladder, Cepheid variables are used to calibrate the supernovae type Ia (SN1a) brightnesses which are then used to calibrate and calculate the Hubble constant.

Now the effect that farther away galaxies show universally a higher red-shift (the incoming light appears redder, weaker) called the cosmological red-shift, is not caused by physical movement through space but rather through expansion of inherent metric of distances in space or ether (depending on your preferred way to talk about properties of ‘empty-space’).

Even then the correction applies all the same, and this effect actually increases the Hubble constant by a little over 1%, or 1 km/s/Mpc; which is not all insignificant, and in fact increases the current contradiction in standard cosmology, named Hubble tension. Bilicki M. and Clements D. [4] published a paper in which done the calculations.

The type Ia supernovae show a remarkably predictable evolution of their brightness with time (called the lightcurve). SN1a in farther and farther away galaxies take longer and longer to dim, and this is an instance of time dilation already well known. What is not discussed however, is if a galaxy had a large inward radial velocity (blue-shift), we would see the an SN1a dim more rapidly than expected.

Another place where this effect would be highly useful is in the analysis of the lightcurves of binary stars. If a binary system has a significantly massive host star and a lower mass yet bright star companion, we could find out the masses of the stars only from their lightcurves! Which is currently considered impossible without spectroscopic data.

Let us see how.

When the companion object travels from eclipse to transit, that is when it emerges from

behind the big star and comes in front, it would appear to travel faster than when it goes from transit to eclipse. This is of course after the mean radial velocity of the whole system has been subtracted, yet it would still not matter as we shall subtract the two periods mentioned above anyway. The difference of the two half-periods would give us $2 \cdot v/c$ (assuming $v \ll c$) and hence we now have the orbital velocity of the companion star. Using the period, we would now have the semi-major axis. Assuming a circular orbit the mass of the host star could be calculated by the Newton's relation $v = \sqrt{GM/R}$.

This shall also work in the case of a general binary system with both stars moving considerably; however the geometry is more complex and we shall see it in a subsequent paper.

Now let us look at the classic example of muons generated by cosmic rays in the upper atmosphere that are detected on the ground. Given their speeds and very short lifetime, we would expect to find very few of them on the ground; yet we find so many. This is explained by time dilation, or space contraction. Even though our transform may look different, it gives us the same result.

In the case of muons coming towards Earth, or the Earth coming towards the muons; the frames/objects are approaching each other instead of growing farther apart.

We have only derived the transform for objects that are receding from each other.

We solve this problem by using time in reverse. We run time backward to see.

Then event 1 is the decay of the muon and event 2 is the birth.

The coordinates of the two events in Earth's frame of reference are $(0, 0)$ and (H, T) respectively. H is the height at which muons are produced and T is the lifetime as observed from the Earth. Note that T is not going to be H/v , where v is muon's speed, recall the example of Betelgeuse we discussed earlier.

Hence $(x_1, t_1) = (0, 0)$; $(x_2, t_2) = (H, T)$ as measured by the Earth.

Let us calculate the primed coordinates, i.e. as measured by the muon.

$$x'_1 = \sqrt{\frac{c+v}{c-v}}(0-0) = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$t'_1 = \sqrt{\frac{c-v}{c+v}} \cdot 0 = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$x'_2 = \sqrt{\frac{c+v}{c-v}} \left(H - \frac{c \cdot v}{c+v} T \right) \quad (30)$$

$$t'_2 = \sqrt{\frac{c-v}{c+v}} T \quad (31)$$

Now since the muon is at rest in its own frame of reference, x'_2 should be equal to 0 as well.

$$\therefore \sqrt{\frac{c+v}{c-v}} \left(H - \frac{c \cdot v}{c+v} T \right) = 0 \rightarrow H = \frac{c \cdot v}{c+v} T \quad (32)$$

Then

$$t'_2 = \sqrt{\frac{c-v}{c+v}} T \quad (33)$$

becomes

$$t'_2 = \sqrt{\frac{c-v}{c+v}} \times \frac{c+v}{c \cdot v} H \quad (34)$$

$$t'_2 = \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}{c} \times \frac{H}{v} \quad (35)$$

$$t'_2 = \frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{H}{v} \quad (36)$$

where $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$.

Let us evaluate it using some rough values.

For $v = 0.995 \cdot c$, $\gamma \approx 10$.

If a muon is produced at $H = 6$ km, it would take $20\mu\text{s}$ to reach the surface with a speed like $0.995 \cdot c$ (this is of course H/v , not the observed time difference).

Hence t'_2 or the time elapsed in the muon frame comes out to be roughly $2\mu\text{s}$; which is a normal muon lifetime.

You could simply swap the frames and discover that for a muon, when $2\mu\text{s}$ pass on its clock, it would also find that clocks on Earth are running slow, which is not very interesting. However, the receding Earth (remember that the time is running backward) would appear $\sqrt{(c+v)/(c-v)}$ times shorter, or about 20 times shorter. However, it would also appear to move half as slowly (remember apparent velocities) and hence it would travel 10 times more distance in a lifetime.

The reverse of this, with time running forward would be that the incoming Earth would appear elongated by a factor of $\sqrt{(c+v)/(c-v)}$ but it would also appear to move at a speed of $(c \cdot v / c - v)$ and the net effect remains the same.

Now we have seen the derivation and some applications of the transform. A lot of work awaits us.

We end our discussion here for now. Hope that the reader has enjoyed our exploration. This view is very different from the standard view, even if it is mathematically equivalent. It may take a while to fully grasp the content of this paper. Stay tuned for future work!

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